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**PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE FORMATION OF THE CIVIL
DEFENSE SERVICE SPECIALISTS IN THE PRIMARY
PREPARATION SYSTEM**

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**ФОРМУВАННЯ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ ФАХІВЦІВ
СЛУЖБИ ЦИВІЛЬНОГО ЗАХИСТУ В СИСТЕМІ
ПЕРВИННОЇ ПІДГОТОВКИ**

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The article highlights the relevance of given issue, which is caused by systematic practice analysis of the primary system vocational training of specialists in the civil defense service, trends in the development of fire and technical education, researches of domestic and foreign scientists and own experience in teaching practice. The directions of psychological and pedagogical sources in which scientists investigated a problem of professional competence formation of specialists of the civil service protection are given. The results of the researches analysis on the questions of the competent approach to the training of qualified specialists are presented, which proved that there is no unambiguous definition of the professional competence concept. The author's interpretation of the concept "competence of a civil defense specialist" are given as the integrated characteristic of the expert identity, reflecting the formation level of professional knowledge, abilities, qualities and practical experience allowing him to carry out successfully the professional activity directed to preservation of life and human health, protection of natural territories and objects in the conditions of the fires emergence, technogenic and natural character emergency situations. The structural components of professional competence of specialists of the civil defense are presented in the article, to which are carried: motivational and valuable, cognitive and operational, reflexive and estimated. Formation levels of specialists' professional competence of civil service defense are determined, namely: high, sufficient and elementary. The prospects of further development of the problem improvement of scientific and methodical ensuring process of professional formation competence of civil defense service specialists are defined.

Key words: competence, professional competence, civil defense service, primary education, educational institutions of the SSU of Ukraine.

У статті наведено актуальність даного питання, яка зумовлена системним аналізом практики системи первинної професійної підготовки фахівців служби

цивільного захисту, тенденцій розвитку пожежно-технічної освіти, досліджень вітчизняних та зарубіжних науковців і власного досвіду викладацької діяльності. Наведено напрями психолого-педагогічних джерел, у яких ученими досліджувалась проблема формування професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту. Викладено результати аналізу досліджень з питань компетентнісного підходу до підготовки кваліфікованих фахівців, який довів, що однозначного визначення поняття професійної компетентності не існує. Наведено авторське тлумачення поняття, «компетентність фахівця служби цивільного захисту» як інтегрованої характеристики особистості фахівця, яка відображає рівень сформованості професійних знань, умінь, якостей та практичного досвіду, що дозволяють йому успішно здійснювати професійну діяльність, спрямовану на збереження життя і здоров'я людей, охорону природних територій та господарських об'єктів в умовах виникнення пожеж, надзвичайних ситуацій техногенного та природного характеру. Обґрунтовано структурні компоненти професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту, до яких віднесено: мотиваційно-ціннісний, когнітивно-операційний та рефлексивно-оцінний. Визначено рівні сформованості професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту, а саме: високий, достатній, елементарний. Окреслено перспективи подальшої розробки проблеми вдосконалення науково-методичного забезпечення процесу формування професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту.

Ключові слова: компетентність, професійна компетентність, служба цивільного захисту, первинна підготовка, навчальні заклади ДСНС України.

Introduction. The modern period of state building in Ukraine requires a new, non-standard vision of the vocational training problem of qualified specialists in the civil defense service. Among the main tasks of the Ukrainian fire-technical educational institutions, the practical training of specialists is becoming more important. It is caused by the fact that difficult working conditions demand from specialists of civil defense service of considerable volume of professional knowledge, abilities, skills and professional and significant personal qualities which allow them to make effective decisions at elimination of the fires, consequences of technogenic catastrophes, natural disasters when it is not only about optimum use of material and financial resources, and, first of all, about people life and health.

Such strict requirements to professional activity of future fire-prevention workers demand a research of process of professional formation competence by specialists of civil defense service of primary vocational training system.

People who are accepted for civil defense service and appointed to positions of private and junior command personnel of the civil defense service, are undergoing initial vocational training, and for the posts of middle and senior commanders of the civil defense service – retraining or specialization in the relevant civil defense institutions (ВПУ, 2013).

Such training is carried out in higher educational establishments of the State Social Insurance Institution of Ukraine and territorial educational and methodical centers of civil defense and safety of vital functions, whose work is regulated by the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “The order of the management staff and specialists whose activities are related to the organization and implementation of measures on civil protection training” of October 23 2013 № 819 (КМУ, 2013, ЖОВТЕНЬ, 23).

The urgency of this issue is determined by the systematic analysis of the system practice of primary vocational training by specialists in the civil defense service, trends in the development of fire and technical education, research of domestic and foreign scientists and own teaching practice.

Detailed studying of psychology and pedagogical sources shows that the formation problem of professional competence of civil service defense specialists was investigated by scientists in the context of the following main directions:

- scientific principles of specialists professional training (N. Abashkina, V. Bykov, P. Volovik, R. Gurevich, V. Evdokimov, I. Zyazyun, O. Kovalenko, N. Nichkalo, T. Naylor, I. Prokopenko, S. Sysoeva, M. Smetansky, A. Trotsko, F. P. Khannik, I. Heister, P. Yakovyshina, T. Yatsenko and others), in particular, the disclosure of the peculiarities of forming a specialist's readiness for professional activity on the basis of a competent approach (N. Bibik, Yu. Boichuk, I. Zimnya, V. Lozova, A. Markova, O. Ovcharuk, O. Pometun, I. Prokopenko, A. Khutorsky and others);

- substantiation of theoretical and methodological principles of specialists preparation in the civil defense service (R. Bezrukavy, A. Bykov, N. Vovchast, A. Dement, L. Iishichkina, M. Kozyar, A. Mayboroda, O. Ostroverh, O. Parubok, V. Sedkovy, T. Tkachenko, M. Tkachuk, A. Khripunova and others).

At the same time, in the psychological and pedagogical science, the process of forming the professional competence of specialists in the civil defense service in the system of primary vocational training was not the subject of a special study. This predetermines the need to resolve existing contradictions regarding the problem under investigation, namely, between: the high level of the demands of the modern society on the professional competence of the civil defense service specialists and the existing practice of primary vocational training; the necessity of purposeful formation of the professional competence of

specialists of the civil defense service in the system of primary vocational training and the lack of scientific and methodological support for this process.

Formulation the purpose of the article and the tasks. The purpose and objectives of the paper are to determine the essence and structure of the professional competence of the civil defense service specialists and to substantiate the appropriate technology of its formation in the process of initial vocational training.

Description of the main material of the article. The development of the economy, based on the innovative model, requires the integration of science and education, a significant increase in the level of training specialists for various sectors of Ukraine. The implementation of the Bologna Process, to which Ukraine has joined, requires the creation of a common scientific and educational space with the same standards of knowledge for all the countries of the European Union, the increasing role of educational institutions in shaping the professional competence of specialists and the development of science. The training of specialists in the civil defense service in Ukraine is regulated by the Laws of Ukraine “On Education”, “On Vocational Education”, the relevant Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, as well as departmental orders.

In modern education, the notion of a competent approach is understood as the direction of the pedagogical process on the formation and development of students’ main (basic) and subject competences. In turn, main competencies are defined as a socially recognized complex of a certain level of knowledge, skills and abilities, attitudes, etc., which can be applied to a broad field of human activity.

It is supposed that a competent person possesses not only knowledge, high moral qualities and is a professional, but also able to act adequately in appropriate situations, applying knowledge and assuming responsibility for his activities.

Competence-based approach assumes accent shift from accumulation of a standard and certain knowledge, skills to development in students of ability practically to work, apply skills and experience of successful actions in situations of professional activity and social practice. Prospects of this approach are that it provides high readiness of young people for successful activity in various spheres of society. Also, it is possible to note that realization of competence-based approach assumes judgment of overall objectives of education in the conditions of its variability. In turn, shifts in understanding of

common goals cause need of changes in approaches and mechanisms of contents and, as a result, in standards of education.

The analysis of researches concerning competence-based approach to training of qualified specialists has proved that unambiguous definition of a concept of professional competence doesn't exist. Often professional competence is identified with professionalism, professional competence. So, for example, E. Zeer treats professional competence as set of professional knowledge, abilities, and also means of professional activity performance (Зееp, 2007, p. 24). D. Raven considers that professional competence is cogitative operations and practical abilities (Pавен, 2001, p. 32). A. Markova insists that competence assumes also a combination of psychological qualities of people which help them independently and responsibly carry out professional duties (Маркова, 1990, p. 83). Yu. Fokin specifies that awareness of requirement and formation of motive belong to elements of professional competence (Фокин, 2002, p. 24).

Competence involves not only the amount of knowledge and experience, but the ability to update the accumulated knowledge and skills and, if it necessary, use them in the process of implementing their professional functions. Most researchers consider competence as a process and result of teaching activity.

It is necessary to notice that the concept “competence” is approximated by the meaning of the concepts “professionalism” and “skill”, which are sometimes considered as a set of certain qualities of a specialist, due to its high level of preparedness, the ability to optimally solve professional problems.

According to this, the professional competence of a future specialist can be considered as a complex, integrated education, which reveals a set of his knowledge, skills, experience, motivation and personal qualities, conditioned readiness for the active realization of the tasks, the content of each its components contains main (informational, regulatory, communicative), operational and intellectual competencies that are provided at different levels of education and training.

Due to the above, competence of the civil defense service specialist can be defined as the integrated characteristic of the expert identity, reflecting the level of formation of professional knowledge, abilities, qualities and practical experience allowing him to carry out successfully the professional activity directed to preservation of people life and health, protection of natural territories

and objects in the conditions of emergence of the fires, emergency situations of technogenic and natural character.

Professional competence of the civil defense service specialists includes such structural components: motivational and valuable, cognitive and operational, reflexive and estimated.

Thus, the motivational and valuable component is characterized by the professional-pedagogical orientation of the future civil defense service specialist for the professional activity and includes a cognitive interest to rescue and fire fighting activity, motivation for mastering professional competence.

The cognitive and operational component is characterized by formation of professional knowledge and abilities which assimilation is necessary for implementation of professional activity.

The reflexive and estimated component assumes formation of ability for self-education, judgments, the analysis and introspection and formation of reflexive abilities.

For determination formation level of professional competence by the civil defense specialist we have specified the corresponding criteria which appear in a number of indicators. Set of criteria allows to estimate the relation to professional problems, formation of interest in mastering of rescue and fire fighting activity, development of professional and personal qualities, formation of professional knowledge and abilities, development of ability to self-education and a reflection of own behavior.

Formation levels of professional competence of civil defense service specialists are determined, namely: high, sufficient and elementary.

For ensuring formation of professional competence we have developed technology which provides the following stages: preparatory, motivational and stimulating, substantial and practical, analytical and productive.

Thus, the preparatory stage is directed at introducing changes to the content of curriculum programs, preparation of the corresponding educational and methodical maintenance, motivational stimulating is focused on ensuring cognitive interest, motivation to mastering rescue and fire fighting activity, awareness of her importance for future professional activity; substantial and practical which provides expansion of a range of professional knowledge, formation of abilities, professional and personal qualities and analytical and productive for which the analysis of the received results and their adjustment is intended.

Conclusions. In the process of initial vocational training of civil defense service specialists it is important to create professional knowledge, abilities, qualities and practical experience which are necessary for achievement of high qualification and use of these achievements in further office activity. Further development is demanded by a problem of scientific and methodical ensuring process improvement of professional competence formation of civil defense service specialists' of primary vocational training system.

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